

ON THE USE OF A PLASTIC NUT INSTEAD OF A METAL NUT IN A LOADED SCREW GEAR

The introduction of new types of materials is one of the conditions for economic growth. The development and introduction of new types of materials into production is of great importance as a means of eliminating dependence on the depletion of mineral reserves.

In the process of designing new parts, the designer tries to create a product that surpasses existing analogues in terms of quality, performance, cost, ergonomics, etc.

Since plastic provides strength, durability and corrosion resistance to chemicals and weather, it is gradually replacing metal as the dominant trend for industrial applications.

The AM8D electric locomotive is a two-axle locomotive with individual frame suspension and one cabin. Electric locomotives are equipped with two braking systems: electric and mechanical. The electric brake is the main type of service brake. The mechanical brake (Fig. 1) is used for emergency stopping of the electric locomotive and braking at parking lots.

Figure 1. Mechanical brake system AM8D

To brake the electric locomotive, the driver uses the steering wheel to rotate the screw 1 in the nut 9 installed in the rocker arm 4. The rocker arm acts on the brake levers 5, which press the cast-iron brake pads 2, 3 to the wheel rims. The resulting

friction force is realized in the form of a braking force between the wheels and rails. The brake levers are suspended on the levers 6, 8. The gaps between the pads and the wheel rims are adjusted by the brake ties 7. The hinged connection of the brake system parts is provided by the fingers 10, 11, 12. Nut 9 (Fig. 2) is made of cast iron of the SCh 12-28 grade and has a mass of 2.8 kg.

Fig. 2. Brake system rocker arm nut

There is a well-known company in Ukraine that offers various plastic nuts on the market. This is a limited liability company "TD "Vector" with an office in Kyiv, offers running nuts for machine tools made of Zedex plastic manufactured by Wolf Kunststoff-Gleitlager GmbH. They offer a wide range of polymer running nuts for service stations also made of German polymer Zedex.

These nuts with trapezoidal thread operate under a load of 8000 N and a rotation speed of 540 rpm. Such a nut replaced the bronze one, which led to a decrease in operating costs, since the plastic nut did not require lubrication and maintenance, and energy consumption was also reduced by reducing friction in the threaded transmission.

This information prompted the authors to think about replacing the cast-iron nut of the rocker arm of the AM8D electric locomotive brake system with a plastic one.

REEK plastic (polyetheretherketone) has become very popular on the polymer market. This is a refractory semi-crystalline plastic that has high strength. It is characterized by high temperature resistance, extremely high rigidity and impact

resistance. In industry, PEEK material is used for the production of parts and components for the aerospace and automotive industries, as well as in the medical field. It is the optimal 3D plastic for technical applications in 3D printing.

Zedex plastic is a thermoplastic composite synthetic material consisting of 98% PEEK. Parts made of TM Zedex materials are able to work for a long time without the use of lubricants.

Due to the extremely low coefficient of dry friction (only 0.08), sufficient strength and rigidity, the use of TM Zedex materials allows you to avoid the lubrication process and thus save lubricants and time.

As a result of calculating the load on the rocker arm nut, a calculated longitudinal load on the nut from the screw side of 8800 N was obtained.

The study of the possibility of using a plastic nut instead of a cast iron nut was carried out in the Fusion 360 computer program of the American company Autodesk.

For this purpose, a 3D model of the nut was developed, which was then investigated using the Simulation option. Fig. 3 shows the properties of the created nut, and Fig. 4 shows the results of determining the mechanical stresses in the nut under a load of 8800 N.

Fig. 3. Properties of PEEK plastic nuts

Fig. 4. Modeling of loading the nut with a longitudinal force of 8800 N

The maximum compressive stress is 26.6 MPa, while the tensile strength limit for this plastic is 90-100 MPa.

Conclusion: The cast-iron nut in the rocker arm of the brake system of the AM8D mine electric locomotive can be replaced with a plastic one, which will reduce its weight (from 2.8 to 0.55 kg), eliminate periodic lubrication, and increase its shelf life.